

Rights of Women in Islam and West: A Comparative Analysis

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Professor Dr. Matloob Ahmad

Chairman, Department of Arabic and Islamic Studies, The University of Faisalabad.

Email: dr.matloobahmed786@yahoo.com

Dr. Uzma Begum

Principal Govt Postgraduate Girls College khrick, Rawalakot, Azad Kashmir.

Email: druzma2017@gmail.com

Muhammad Qasim

Doctoral Candidate, Department of Islamic Studies, The University of Faisalabad,
Pakistan.

Email: m.qasim2937@gmail.com

Mubashar Hasnain

M.Phil Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies, The University of Faisalabad,
Pakistan.

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Abstract

This is an article with the topic “Comparative analysis of the rights duties of woman in Islamic civilization” Muslim women’s role is highlighted in this topic through Quranic guidance and Ahadees of Hazrat Muhammad (S.A.W), and through the status of woman in the pre-Islam era is also highlighted. Besides this, it reflects different rights and duties of woman. In this article comparative analysis of both the Islamic and Western civilizations is highlighted. At the end after deducting result from the discussions conclusion is presented. Before Islam the woman was treated as wretched element of the society and thrown in the darkness of ignorance. She was hopeless and cannot hope for her evolution. The Islam raised awareness and protested against this cruel attitude and taught that the whole life revolves around both man & woman. The Holy Prophet (P.B.U.H) provide guidance and teachings regarding the most ignored gender (the woman) as no champion of woman’s rights can promote this cause and with such zeal and zest. The woman is respectable either she is in western or Islamic civilization. The women should be respected everywhere. If we analyse the western civilization, we will come to know the reason of accepting Islam by woman is that the Islam suggests separate domains for man and woman. For this particular reason western ladies are accepting Islam and the logic behind this is that the Islam is the religion of nature, it is complete code of life and it is the only religion which addresses the nature of woman and it protects her rights and respect.

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Islam gave her a status which she cannot imagine.

Keywords: Holy Prophet (P.B.U.H), Rights of Women, Islam, West, Quranic, Ahadees, life, respect

Objective of the study

No plan can serve the humanity in its true spirit which neglects the position of the woman in society. We cannot think of a society which could be run solely by the men. Men and women both are complimentary to each other. Neither a woman can live without a man, nor a man could be fully independent of a woman. Their needs towards each other are multi-dimensional such as social, sexual and psychological. Social structure of a society demands them to work together on equal footings on the one hand and their sexual desires compel them to seek peace and satisfaction in each other to form a successful society on the other. The existing civilization failed to establish peaceful social co-existence among man and woman by mishandling the sexual issue between them. By dragging the woman into the circles that are specified for the man in a society, the modern civilization has established a negative social relation among the both genders. As a result, we can see a woman striving hard to save her position amongst the men and disregarding those duties that are assigned to her by the nature. The basic duty of a woman is to make the home such a peaceful place that take away all the tiredness of his husband. Due to this reason, a good wife is declared as a heavenly gift for he husband.

Amongst the civilizations of the world, Islam is the only system that gave a woman a better position and more protection of her rights. The other civilizations have driven the woman to such a hillarious stage where no remedy is available to her else the destitute. The present civilization provoked the sexual desire and it took the possession of mind of the human beings. As a result, abstention from doing some beneficial work for society and increasing tendency of delusion is observed amongst the members of the society. One who has the understanding of these social conditions must accept the above-mentioned statement. The establishment of these unethical relations between man and woman has shaken the foundations of the society and left a man at such vulnerable stage where he is deprived of satisfaction and peace in spite the availability of thousands of (man made) means of amusement and recreation. In these situations, Islam has drawn the different picture of the woman on the canvas which was not a mutilation of the whole scenery, rather this is a creation of new and different map for this period. whether the world accepts it or not, we believe that only the Islamic society has laid solid foundations for the sexual and social relations of man and woman. the successful relations can only be established upon these foundations, any other basis for these relationships will certainly lead to the failure.

Status of woman before Islam.

Studies of pre-Islamic Arab Societies reveal to us the vulnerable conditions of the woman. they had no value at all and were treated like the household rather than a member of the family. A man was free to have as many wives as he wishes and treat them according to his will. It was not only a trend amongst the... but also in Eliteclass of the society to have partnerships in wives. Their behaviour with the woman was barbarian and they were humiliated like animals.

Quran depicts the true picture of their feelings regarding a woman.

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When if one of them receiveth tidings of the birth of a female, his face remainneth darkened, and he is worth inwardly.¹

According to the Hindu Religious traditions: it was impossible to terminate the marriage contract between a man and woman (in whatever circumstances may be) even their life turned to the hell. The woman has no right to marry with another person even after the death of her first husband. In India, the wife was compelled to die with him on his death pile by way of burning. This ritual of Brahman Civilization has been continuously practiced till the 17th century when it was unapproved by the religious authorities. In this era woman had no share in her husband's property nor she had any right of education.²

The condition of the woman was not better in Christianity and Judaism as well. There is a clear commandment in gospel: "that the man and woman are bonded in a relation by Allah and only he has the authority to break it". The jews consider a woman unclean and dirty during her heavy days when she is naturally not able to cohabit with men. They dislike to have an ordinary interaction with her in those days.

There was no law that regulates the affairs of maintenance of a woman nor a woman had any legal protection for any wrong done to her by her husband.

A husband had a right to deprive her wife from being a sharer of his inheritance. on the other hand, no one could be object him to be the legal heir of his wife. In the old Jewishrulings, the man had been declared as a master of her wife and his murder by his wife was termed as small mutiny. The penalty for this crime was that the offender must have been set into fire.

Status of woman in Islamic Society

Islam is the only religion that gave a woman the position which she was deserved. Quran prescribes equal status and rights for women in all aspects of daily life as well as the religious affairs such as prayer, fasting, pilgrimage and commercial transactions etc.

It is clearly mentioned in Quran:

And whoso doeth goodworks, whether of male or female, and he (or she) is a believer, such will enterparadise and they will not be wronged the dint in a date stone.³

In another verse it is described as under:

And the believers, men and women, are protecting friends of one another; they enjoining the right and forbid the wrong, and they establish worship and they pay the poor-due, and they obey Allah and His messenger. As for these, Allah will have mercy on them. Lo! Allah is Mighty, Wise.⁴

It is evident from above mentioned verses of Quran that the Islam gave the equal status and equal rights to the women to that of the men. We find no reference of such a dignity for a woman in any other civilization.

The human beings are social in his nature. When a child came into this world he sees a folk of destitute peoples of his family around him.Amongst them are his father, uncle, aunt, grandfather and grandmother etc. the child lead his entire life from his infancy, then his youth to his adulthood under care and love of these relatives.When he starts his practical life he has a strong feeling of recompense them.The same feeling enables him to live a successful social life.

Study of the human history shows that Allah created all the human beings from a noble pair

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of man and woman i.e. Adam and Eve. Then he spread their progeny to all around the world. O mankind! Lo! We have created you male and female, and have made you nations and tribes that you may know one another. Lo! The noblest of you, in the sight of Allah, is the best in conduct. Lo! Allah is knower, Aware.⁵

These verses vested a feeling of self-confidence to the woman and taught her that the criteria of preference according to Allah is only the piety and not the gender. It is the impact of these verses that the women proved their worth in every aspect of life. They came forward as best of mothers, great teachers, intellectuals and authors. They transferred their knowledge of these fields to the thousands of other women.

In the beginning the progeny of the Adam and Eve lived as a single nation and followed a single religion. They spoke a single language and there were no differences between them. But as soon as their number increased they spread around the different parts of the world. Due to this expansion, they divided into different casts, nations and the tribes. The geographical division affected their language, their attire and their way of life. But they are in fact the progeny of Adam and Eve laid the foundation of the human race in this universe. Rest of all human beings are their offspring.

If a woman feareth ill treatment from her husband, or desertion, it is no sin for them twain if they make terms of peace between themselves. Peace is better.⁶

Equality in Rights for woman

Woman has been considered a trivial entity and denied of any significant role in the society. This was so till the advent of Islam. She was in such a low position in the society that disabled her to think of about her development. Islam opposed these mall practices and displayed her true picture to the world.

No advocate of human Rights can prescribe a description of women rights more precisely than that of the Holly prophet □ which are evident from his teachings.

Abu Saeed Khudri narrated that the Prophet (P.B.U.H) □ has said: "No one has three or two daughters or sisters, and he fears Allah regarding them and is kind to them, except that he will enter Paradise."

It is narrated that a man amongst the fellows of Abdullah ibn Umar (may Allah be pleased with them both) celebrated the death of her three daughters. When Abdullah knew that he became angry with him and said: Do You give them sustenance?

The first duty of a man after the marriage contract to pay the dower of his wife wholeheartedly.

It is advised by Allah in Surah Nisa:

And give unto the women (whom ye marry) free gift of their marriage⁷

Dower is the exclusive right of woman and she is the only authority to waive it. It should be fixed according the financial capacity of the husband and it is unapproved by the Holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) to fix the dowers in huge amount for the purpose of show off.

The second duty of the husband is to provide maintenance to her wife. This should be too according to his capacity.

Men are in charge of women, because Allah hath made the one of them to excel the other, and because they spend of their property (for the support of women).⁸

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Ownership and Inheritance

No religion except Islam gave the woman right to have her own property. Islam accredited right of personal liberty and inheritance for a woman and made proper instructions to protect her liberty from any kind of transgression.

In surah Nisa, it is clearly mentioned that a woman has a right to inherit as like to the man. This right is granted to her for her financial stability

The verse says:

Unto the men (of a family) belongeth a share of that which parents and near kindred leave, and unto the women a share of that which parents and near kindred leave, weather it be little or much – a legal share.⁹

When a woman get married she became entitled to inherit from her husband as well as her parents.¹⁰

Legal Status of Ila

Islam done justice to the woman in every walk of life, its clear manifestation can be seen in the case of Ila. *In ila a husband discontinue sexual relations with her wife for a specific period of time, but he can not exceed this time limitation. This commandment is mentioned in Surah Baqrah:*

Those who forswear their wives must wait four months; then, if they change their mind, lo! Allah is Forgiving, Merciful. And if they decide upon divorce (let them remember that) Allah is Hearer, Knower.¹¹

When a man swears that he will not have sexual relations with his wife for four months, it is termed as Ila in Fiqh. If they are not able to reconcile within these four months the only treatment is pronouncement of Talaq.

In this case the opinion of Malki jurists seems more accurate who are on the view that if a man discontinues marital relations with her wife without swearing it will also termed as Ila.¹²

Case of Intervening Marriage

If a man wants to remarry her divorced wife it is not possible for him to do so without an intervening marriage. But it is not lawful for first husband to persuade the second husband to pronounce talaq to the woman to break this intervening marriage. And an intervening marriage with the condition of talaq will be considered as fornication and not an Islamic marriage. This strict rule is laid down to stop the men from pronouncing exclusive talaq to their wives at once without taking into account the consequences of such act.¹³

It is narrated on the authority of Ibn Abbas that the Messenger of Allah said:

The Curse of Allah be upon the one who marries a divorced woman with the intention of making her lawful for her former husband, and upon the one for whom she is made lawful!¹⁴

Right of Iddat (Waiting Period)

Literal meaning of Iddat is to count something. According to fiqh it is a specific time period that has to be waited by women after talaq or the death of her husband. Wisdom behind this rule is the preservation of progeny from any kind of adulteration. Waiting period for a divorced woman is three periods and for a woman whose husband has died is four months and ten days. If a woman is pregnant at the time of talaq or his husband's death then she must

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wait till the delivery of child.¹⁵

Women's Right of Khula

Amongst the right granted to women by Islam is the Khula. This right is available to her at any stage of her marital life. A woman can exercise this right when she finds her husband unable to fulfil her sexual desire or to pay her proper maintenance. Another reason for exercising khula is the physical and mental torture by the husband. A woman can herself offer her husband to divorce her in lieu of dower or other property or gift, if she dislike him or she feels impossible to fulfil her matrimonial duties. If the husband agrees with her, it is well and good, otherwise, she can raise the matter to the arbitration or the court.¹⁶

Some jurists do not accept for a woman the right of kula and interpret the commandment of shariah regarding the khula in a different way. But it is admitted by the shariah and it is, in fact, beauty of the Islam that it accommodates all kind of natural rights. Sometimes a woman faces such unfavorable conditions that made impossible for her to keep marital ties with her husband. Refusal of this right for woman in such vulnerable condition is a due to lack of understanding of Islamic teachings and ignorance of ground realities.

Narrated Ibn 'Abbas: The wife of Thabit bin Qais came to the Prophet (P.B.U.H) and said, "O Allah's Apostle! I do not blame Thabit for defects in his character or his religion, but I, being a Muslim, dislike to behave in un-Islamic manner if I remain with him." On that Allah's Apostle said to her, "Will you give back the garden which your husband has given you as Mahr?" She said, "Yes." Then the Prophet (P.B.U.H) ordered to Thabit, "O Thabit! Accept your garden, and divorce her once."¹⁷

Khula has a status of one irrevocable talaq. After this talaq the husband has no right to have the marital relations with her divorced wife without remarrying her as it is against the essence of khula, because the woman has paid the compensation to the husband. However, it is lawful for them to remarry with each other because khula is not the final talaq. Waiting period for woman after khula is passage of one menstrual cycle. In fact, this time period is prescribed only to assure that the women is not pregnant.¹⁸

It is narrated that the slave girl of Safiyya bint abi Ubaid took khula in lieu of whole dower. (When it is reported to Abdullah ibn Umar) he did not disregard her act.¹⁹

It is also narrated that Rabi bint muawwiz ibn afra and her paternal aunt both came to Abdullah ibn Umar and told her that she took khula from her husband in the era of caliph Uthman, when it is reported to Usman he did not disapprove it. On listening this, Aabdullah ibn umar said the waiting period for a woman is same either she got khula or divorced by her husband.²⁰

Lian

When the husband and wife accuse each other upon the allegations of adultery, it is called Lian. The lian becomes compulsory when a husband directly alleges his wife for adultery or refuses the legitimacy of the children who born to her wife. When a similar case has been presented before the Holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) ﷺ, he said to the spouses taht:Allah knows very well that whom one of you both is liar and does the liar repent from his or her act. When both of them rejected this plea, the Prophet (P.B.U.H) tried the case according the injunction of Quran. He first ordered the husband to swear Allah four times that his allegation upon his

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wife is true, and fifth time that if he be wrong in his allegation then the curse of Allah be upon him. In the same way, he ordered the woman to swear Allah four times that the charge against her is wrong and fifth time that the wrath of Allah upon her if the husband is telling the truth. After that the Prophet (P.B.U.H) said: "this procedure is incumbent upon everyone who has same charge against her wife, till the day of judgement and the separation in the result thereto is also till the day of judgement."²¹

Forum for the cases of Lian:

The case of Lian is tried in a court of justice (competent to hear the case). In a case of Lian the spouses have always an option to accept or reject the charge. If both pleads innocent the judge will issue the decree of separation after due procedure of Lian mentioned above. This separation has an eternal affect and does not annul the dower. The same is reported from Prophet (P.B.U.H) and has a status of precedent in case of Lian.

Option of Puberty

Khiaar is an Arabic term which means: option or choice. The right of a boy or a girl on attaining puberty to approve or disapprove their marriage that was contracted by their Parents or Gaurdian in their childhood. This is a case that requires the juridical debate. A lot of such cases have been presented to the Messenger of Allah and he decided the cases on their merit. Option of puberty is more concerned with the girls as a boy has a right to divorce his wife at any time.

Abdullah ibn Abbas narrated that a virgin girl came to the Holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) and pleaded that her father contracted her marriage against her will. she further pleaded that she dislike her husband. The Prophet (P.B.U.H) granted her the right to approve or disapprove the marriage.²²

Missing Husband (مفقود الخبر)

A (مفقود الخبر) is man who is not known to a long period neither his life or death is ascertained by the efforts to search him. Quran and Hadith are silent in this regard.

Juristic Opinion:

Variety of opinion is reported regarding the case of Missing Husband amongst the Companions, Followers and the Jurists. One of the opinion is that a wife should wait her missing husband for a period of four years. It is reported from Umar, Usman, Abdullah ibn Abbas and Abdulllah bin Umar amongst the Companions. Saeed bin Musayyab, Zuhri and Nakhai amongst the followers have the same opinion. While Ali and Abdullah bin Masood amongst the companions are of the view that a wife should wait her missing husband till his return or the assurance of his death.²³ Imam Abu Hanifa and Sufyan Thauri amongst the jurist have opted for this view.

Duties of woman in Islam

Obedience of Husband

The most important duty that is imposed upon a woman by Islam is the obedience of husband. The supreme authority in this universe is Allah SWT and It is duty of the human beings to obey Him and accept all his commandments like a ruler. Then a family is the smallest unit in any country and the husband is the head of this unit. The kids and the wife are duty bound to obey him. All the institutions of the heavens and earth are doing their functions with the same sense of obedience. This sense of obedience is necessary to maintain the law and order. Without this sense the system of this universe will be derailed due to inconsistency of

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commandments.

It is narrated that Zainab bint Ali had never disobeyed her husband. That's why their marital life was very peaceful. Abdullah, her husband also took a lot of care for her. Although Zainab had slaves and maids at her home, but she preferred to do work at home herself.

It is prime duty of the wife to obey all the orders of her husband which are not against the command of Allah. This rule is laid down in various traditions of Holy prophet ﷺ.

It is narrated by Abu Huraira that the Prophet (P.B.U.H) said: a woman should not keep fast other than that of Ramadan without the permission of her husband.

Abu Said narrated this tradition with different words as the Holy Prophet (P.B.U.H) forbade a woman from keeping (optional) fast without the permission of her husband.²⁴

Abu Huraira reported that the Messenger of Allah said: If I were to command anyone to prostrate to anyone other than Allah, I would have commanded women to prostrate to their husbands.²⁵

These traditions are clearly indicating that a woman cannot perform optional ibadah without the permission of her husband.

Patience & Serenity

Second duty of a wife is that she should show a great deal of patience in her domestic life and take keen interest. Joy and sorrow are part of life. If a husband had low income the life goes hand to mouth but a compromising wife tries to manage it well. This sense of sacrifice and altruism bring the real happiness and pleasure in the life. A muslim woman should try to face the hardships of life with patience and courage and not show her concerns to her husband.

It is reported by Anas that the little son of Abu Talha who was sick died during his absence. Her wife covered the child up as if he were sleeping, and left him in a corner of the house. Then she prepared the dinner for Abu Talha. When Abu Talha came to the house he asked about the health of the kid. The wife replied he is well now and not let him know about the death of child. The narrator said that the Abu Talha spent the night making out with her wife. At morning, he took the bath and when he was about to leave the house to go to Messenger of Allah her wife told her about the death of child. Abu Talha came to the Prophet (P.B.U.H) and offered Fajar prayer with him. After that he told him the story of night. The Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said, "May Allah bless you for last night. Sufyan Thauri narrated that he met a person amongst the Ansar who told him that: Abu Talha had nine sons after that who all were renowned scholars and reciters of Quran.²⁶

Loyalty

A woman must be loyal to her husband. She should guard her honour, wealth and family in his absence. It is narrated by Umme Salma that the apostle of Allah said: If a woman dies while her husband was pleased with her, she will enter Paradise.²⁷

Abdullah ibn Amr reported: The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him, said, "*The world is provision and the best provision in the world is a righteous woman.*"²⁸

To guard the husband's house and protect his wealth is the responsibility of the wife and by doing so, she will actually protect her own house and wealth. ²⁹To take interest in the management and affair of the home is also a part of its protection. Such examples are found in the conduct of Aisha and Fatimah. Aisha had used to wash the clothes of Holy Prophet (P.B.U.H) and oil his head along with the other routine matters. It is narrated by Hassan: that

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her mother Fatima daughter of Messenger had used to do all the domestic works at her home, such as, preparation of meal, grinding of grains, washing of clothes and sweeping. she also took care of the children like to bathe them and changing of their clothes. But it is a misfortune that women in our society do not fulfil their duties regarding their husband rather they keep disturbing them on petty matters.

Duties of Woman as a Mother

A woman as a mother has a high status in Islam. Islam declared that the paradise is beneath the feet of mother. A mother is a great gift of heaven. It is unbearable to her to see her kids in any trouble and they feel an utmost peace and relaxation in her lap. Her kindness for her children is exceptional. To give birth of a child is a painful procedure and it enables a woman to achieve a high rank near to Allah. Due to this difficult role, Allah laid the commandments for humans to treat their parents with love and affection.

Holly Quran says:

And We have commanded unto man kindness toward parents. His mother beareth him with reluctance, and bringeth him forth with reluctance, and the bearing of him and the weaning of him is thirty months.³⁰

Abu Huraira narrated that The Prophet (P.B.U.H)(peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said: "Three prayers are undoubtedly answered: the prayer of one who is wronged, the prayer of the traveller and the prayer of a father for his child."³¹

Mothers should train and teach their kids Islamic manners like prayer and fasting. They should follow the Fatimah as a role model in this regard. She used to read Quran at times when she was making her children to a sleep.

The Prophet (P.B.U.H) has implanted the respect of woman in the minds of his followers. He taught them that a woman is a way to heaven as a mother, a partner of life as a wife and comfort of life as a sister and light of this world as a daughter.

Prohibition of disturbing the husband

A muslim woman should not make unnecessary demands to her husband rather they should manage their needs according to the financial capacity of the husband. Big houses, cars and money in excess are the luxuries of life but these cannot bring the satisfaction and peace in a man's life which is actual wealth. If the wealth had a value near Allah, the Prophet (P.B.U.H) and pious people had never unlike it. A muslim woman is very fortunate to have the Aisha and Fatima as a role model for her life. they were exceptional wives and women in this world.

Hijab (veil)

It is the responsibility of a husband to compel her wife to put a veil upon her while going outside and not to mix with men unnecessarily. Quran laid this in as under:

*O Prophet (P.B.U.H) tell thy wives and thy daughters and the women of the believers to draw their cloaks close round them (when they go abroad). That will be better, so that they may be recognised and not annoyed. Allah is ever Forgiving, Merciful.*³²

The strict adherence of the wives of Prophet (P.B.U.H) can be judged by the act of aisha in a battle when she could not identify her brother due to veil. The other woman should follow their conduct regarding the veil like the other matters. History reveals that the Prophet (P.B.U.H)wives gave up the grandeur and high status of this worldly life for the company of

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Prophet (P.B.U.H) They faced hardships for him and rejected the luxuries of life. They adopted poverty and lead a compromising life within the limited resources of livelihood. They lead their entire lives according the commandments of Holly prophet □ and manifest this obedience in all the acts of daily life. They dedicated themselves for this noble cause. They assisted the Holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) in the matters of religion. They not only played their role as preachers but also participated in teaching and war. They purified the society from the obsolete customs and traditions according to the teaching of Prophet (P.B.U.H) They dedicated their lives for the maintenance of orphans and widows, help of helpless and needy. Ummahat al moumineen have done all the housework like grinding of grains, fetching of water with their own hands. Beside domestic work, they also participated in trading and agriculture. They had got their share from booty as well. They owned a lot of wealth but hey had usually spent their earning to help the poor and for wellbeing of the destitute people for the sake of Allah. They faced the hunger by sacrificed for the sake of Allah. By their conduct they set a great example for the entire women of Islamic civiliazation.

Rights and Duties of Woman in Western Civilization

In this part, we will analyse the position of women, her achievements and troubles in western society. Western culture has given the freedom to the woman. She has no responsibilities of home and family. They lead their life in pleasure, half-dressed rather naked, in the company of men at parks, restaurants and theaters. She has no liability of children. She wants to fully enjoy her freedom that which she got after a lot of struggle. She doesn't care of ethics, religion and morality as they are old fashioned and act as a barrier to his freedom.

Absolute Independence

Western woman considered the marriage as a prison and this concept badly shattered her chastity and free her from every kind of responsibilities. Western society became a folk of animals due to this free style life. men and women live together like the animals without marriage. There is no need of any formal agreement between them that impose any liabilities of relationship. Every person lives his own life even the Care of old parents is not the responsibility of children. A lot of institutions have been established to fulfil that duties which were done by a woman alone in her house. This division demolished the institution of family and badly affected the new generation.

Obedience to the Husband

If we study the Jewish and Christian civilization, we observe the woman as a humiliated and oppressed class of the society. It is clearly mentioned in gospel "that the man and woman are bonded in a relation by Allah and only he has the authority to break it". The wedlock between a man and a woman can only be terminated when the allegation of adultery is proved against one of the spouses. According to Jewish Law: A husband can divorce his woman at any time but a wife has no way to get rid of her husband whatever the circumstances may be.³³ Jew men have no ordinary interaction with their wives in their menstrual cycle even they don't like to touch those things that are touched by a women her heavy days. in this way, the marriages are contracted in the so-called civilized western society. System of divorce is even worse than the marriage.

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Duties of a woman as a wife

Family life in the west has been demolished. For her lust and freedom the western woman got rid of the family life and living her according to her wish and whims. Immorality and wickedness is a necessary part of their life. the peaceful family life has been vanished.

Contribution of mother in children's upbringing

If we see a mother's role in western society we will observe that it is considered a great fuss to have the children and take care of them. Those mothers who have children also having no time for their upbringing. She is more involved in outdoor activities and ignored her responsibilities towards her family and home.³⁴

Right to have specialization in education or an art.

Another reason to ruin the family life of Europe is increasing tendency of having specialization in a field of knowledge or an art. Every member of society wants to achieve a high position in his or her profession. Sometimes it happens that both spouses has different specialization, and this difference makes them unattractive to each other. They could not develop understanding due to this difference and hence no healthy communication between both takes place. They only make formal discussions between them and then involve in their own specialized field. Then they both feel loneliness and get bored from family life. with the passage of time, these differences worsens and turn into quarrels and result into separation and divorce.³⁵

Rights and Duties of woman as a Mother

Position of the Parents in western Societies is not a hidden fact. They are admitted to old age homes where they live in complete isolation from their children. This is not their own choice rather their siblings have left them alone due to the destruction of family system. They are separated by their families and considered as useless entity of the society. They have been left to live with their memories, waiting for their dear ones for months. They are only familiar with one who serve them food and other utilities of life. they keep waiting for the phone calls of their loved ones but they have no time to call them. They often pass their time reading books, watching television and surfing internet. Their hobby is to remember those people who were a part and parcel of their life. ³⁶

Gender Equality

Europe is the biggest advocate of gender equality. But it was not so before a century or more when the woman was a victim of male chauvinism. No law was there to provide her relief against these humiliations. English law considered the both spouses as a single legal personality after the marriage by merging the wife's into her husband's. Her property and debts were owned by her husband on the basis of said principle. A woman has only way to retain her property by making an agreement prior to her marriage with his to be husband.

Right of maintenance and inheritance

There was no law that regulates the affairs of maintenance of a woman nor a woman had any legal protection for any wrong done to her by her husband. A man had a right to deprive her wife to be his legal heir but on the contrary a woman had no such right. A woman was not free to make any contract or to do a job for her own sustenance. She had no right to marry with a

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man of her own choice.

Status of woman as a daughter

A daughter had been considered as a property of her parents. Their marriage had been contracted by their parents to the person of the parent's choice. These marriages were in fact a form of trade by which parents sell their daughters. Was this really a gender equality that is advocated by west?³⁷

Status of Husband in Western Culture and Right of Wife

Before the advent of Christianity, the man was considered as the absolute master of his wife in England. There was no penalty for him for any wrong doing against the woman. He was a right to leave her wife but a woman had no such right. In the traditional law of England a man was considered the master of her wife and treated her like a king. The commission of his murder by her wife termed as small mutiny and penalty for this offence was to set her on fire. Till today, the English law regulates many issues with a sense of complete authority of a man over his wife. In the marriages solemnized in the church, a woman must take an oath to obey her husband for her whole life which she is legally bound to fulfil. She can do nothing without the consent of her husband. Nor she can earn money, if she does it automatically becomes the property of her husband. English law never granted her the rights equal to the slaves.³⁸ The industrial triumph of Europe led many people to wrongfully admire the western culture and lifestyle. They think that west is like a paradise and follow every western tradition and adopt their life style. They have no knowledge of real face of Europe. When they will perceive this reality, it will be too late for them; when their family system will completely collapse. Many social scientists and philosophers now perceived this reality that the western notions of daily life are misleading. Unfortunately, the west has crossed all the limits of immorality and wickedness where they have no way to return. According to an American philosopher: "that the reformation in family life by following those rules which are necessary to lead a family and nation to the way of happiness. Most important among these are obedience of husbands by wives and love to the wives by husbands and fulfilment of their duties".

Western woman and concept of nudity

It is the general perception of the west that the veil is a barrier to the progress and development of a woman and by imposing veil upon women Islam has limited their freedom. The freedom of women to them is to be open headed, fascinated and free to mix with men. Feminism movement which is based on the gender equality driven the western society to the obscenity, immorality and nudity. The willful fornication is not considered as a sin at all. Homosexuality and same sex marriages are legally permitted. Legitimacy is granted to those children who are born to a prostitute. Most of the worries faced by the west is due to the freedom of woman that absolutely changed the picture of west. family system, drug abuse, adultery, pre- marriage childbirth, high rate of illegitimate children, sexual diseases, gender change, child abuse, common trend of suicide, all are the by products of the gender equality.³⁹

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Comparative analysis

Firstly, the writer has briefly discussed the status of woman in Islamic society. Then she has given a description of rights and duties of women in western society. In this part, a comparative analysis will be made on the basis of above mentioned discussion. This topic requires lengthy debate, but the author made an endeavor to present it concisely.

Although, the western woman has got some achievements in nineteenth century. These are limited to their participation in government institutes and to facilitate them in their daily life. These are essential requirements of a democratic societies. This has been possible after the industrial development but it is not a real success as it is a right of every ordinary woman. In fact, every body is responsible to Allah regarding his/her duties. In Europe, the obscenity and vulgarity is termed as freedom of a woman. But the sophisticated people considers it a wrath. This class favors to regain the chastity of woman and this change in the minds of western people is satisfactory. According to an English writer:

“Europe has never given freedom to woman but gave a plan to ruin her.”

The freedom that granted by the islam to the woman is crystal clear. This freedom does not affect the chastity, grace and mental and physical abilities of women. This is the real freedom. Excessive divorce cases not only disturbed a class of the wise people of Europe but also put an extra workload on the courts. Nudeness, vulgarity, coeducation and free interaction of men and women in business are reasons of increasing rate of divorce. These factors develop temporary attraction between both sexes and provoke them to have marital or sexual relations between them. But as soon as this temporary phase ends, differences takes place between them which result to an end of relations. A large number of divorce cases are due to these temporary attractions.

If the European thinkers want to get rid all of these troubles they should promote the Islamic way of marriage.

The quranic directives for women provide ideological foundation for her life. Today this ideology can save a Muslim woman from a powerful attack of western culture upon the Islamic societies.

Prophet (P.B.U.H) focused on the establishment of a society which a woman should be given an honorable position. He advised kind treatment for women and declared that the best amongst the people is that who is best towards his wife. He granted many rights to the women that were not available to them before. He urged the woman to get education and allowed her to get marry with a man of his own choice. He also granted the right of Khula to the women. All these rights have raised the status of a woman in the society.

Islam prescribed a reasonable way of divorce that is pronouncement of one talaq at one time. Unfortunately, this way is not practiced in society due to the ignorance of Islamic teachings. Most of the men pronounce three talaq at a time which cause to break the family. This is regarded as an innovation and a sinful act in Islam. They don't know that the one talaq fully serves the objective that is served by three talaqs and it can also be revoked. The educated people are also unaware of the Islamic way of family life due to the lack of religious education. Family system that is a foundation stone of society is declining day by day in the west. Peaceful environment of home which is the basis of the healthy growth of humanity has vanished. Relation of a man and woman by marriage that serves the civilization became weaker than a cobweb. Production of human race is tried to be stopped by birth

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control and abortion. Wrong concept of moral equality between men and women gave rise to their equality in immorality. Those acts of Obscenity which have been considered shameful for even men are fully adopted by women without any shame.

The second reason that shaken the foundation of family system is financial exploitation of woman that made her independent of men. The old notions of earning by men and home management by women have been changed. Now the both are earning money and the home management is run by foreign agencies. This change ended all the basis of the relation of man and woman except the sexual desire. This basis can not bind them to keep an eternal relation and formation of a family. A woman who earns her sustenance herself and has no need of a man for her protection could not be compelled to accept a man's supremacy for merely the satisfaction of her sexual desires. For what reason should be limited her freedom? Why should she bear the burden of a family? Specially, when the notion of moral equality has lifted all the barriers in the way to fully enjoy free sex life. sense of guilt has died with the religion.

She has no fear of society as it does not disgrace her on becoming a prostitute, rather it appreciates her. Unwanted birth is controlled by use of contraceptives. If, this method did not work, the option of abortion is available. If it fails the sin can be hidden by murdering the newly born. If maternal sentiments prohibited a woman from killing her illegitimate child, it is also well and good to have it, because the issue of unmarried mother and illegitimate child has a lot of favour in western society and nobody will dare to show any negative feeling towards them. Who will do so will be blamed for backwardness.

Protection of morality is the primary object of Family law of islam. it prohibits Zina (adultery) and demands its followers to follow a strict moral code for sexual relations to preserve their chastity and modesty and for the protection of society from obscenity and evilness. That's why the nikah is termed as Hisn in Quran which means fort. the Islamic law strengthens this fort that is built to preserve the worthy values of morality. But if the nikah does not serve this purpose and it is an apprehension to cross the limits prescribed by Allah, it is better to break this relation. That's why it is prescribed for those who swear to refrain themselves from sexual relations with their wives to not cross the limits of four months. If they do not want to restore their relationship, they are ordered to divorce the wife, to protect the boundaries prescribed by Allah. Similarly, the men with more than one wives are strictly demanded to have justice amongst all the wives. If they could not they have no right to keep them all.

The khula is also prescribed for the same purpose. If a woman is not happily living with her husband or does not feel attraction towards himself, she has a right to ask khula in lieu of money. Because, the real relations are based upon love, affection and compromise and not upon coercion or intimidation.

Fraternization between man and woman is continuously promoting the vulgarity and nudity and exposition of beauty amongst the women. Men and women are naturally invested a sense of attraction towards each other. This is a powerful feeling and the open interaction between men and women provokes the both sense to make themselves more and more striking to each other. The change in moral values made it acceptable to the society. When enticement and luring by the women is admired in a society, it results in nudity and obscenity by crossing the limits of exposition of beauty.

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Desire of luring men is so much increased and rapidly growing day by day that it is not fulfilled merely wearing the tight dresses, applying blushes and adopting all means of fashion and make up rather it drives the women to the nudity. Life style based on these wrong notions is burning the fire of lust in the hearts of people termed as art to disguise the right minds. This wrath is destructing the whole society and spoils those capabilities of man that are necessary for human development. Those who are slave of their evil thinking, who a new form of hejan and feeling of sexuality in every moment of their life, who are fully captured by evilness, whose blood is running by nudity, vulgarity, music, how can they achieve those level of calmness which is necessary for healthy and creative activities in the life. A nation which is itself a victim of ecstasy and lust can not even think to provide a healthy and peaceful environment to their next generations. As soon as they got young the menace of evilness captured them.

To keep a society clean, Primary teaching of Islam for men and women to lower down their gaze. This is mentioned in Quran and Hadith. The Holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) said: The fornication of the eyes is the evil glance.

Allah addressed His Prophet (P.B.U.H) in the respect of faithful men as: "Tell the believing men to lower their gaze and be modes"⁴⁰. But how it is possible for them to protect their eyes from evil sight if women will manifest their beauty. That why it is commanded the women to hide themselves. As, protection of valuables from theft is possible by keeping them in a safe place a woman's safety is in veil. The Prophet (P.B.U.H) informed the muslim women of these threats as a father does in the case of his own daughters. His teachings include: Whole Body of the women is *Awrah* accept her hands and face and she is not permitted to expose it before stranger males except her husband. Nor she can wear a very tight dress that make her body parts prominent. The holly Prophet (P.B.U.H) resembles the woman with a hidden thing when she comes out the Satan stares at her. Quran commanded the muslim men if they ask for something to women must ask it behind the curtain. Islam prohibits the meeting of a man and a woman secretly, rather it dislikes the open mixing of men and women. It further forbids to enter someone's house without permission to preserve the privacy. A special precaution for the women is not to speak with strangers in alluring manner, because it causes temptation to a person of evil thinking. No civilization other than islam takes so much care of women's modesty and chastity. A woman can attain a noble position in the society only by following the holly teachings of Prophet (P.B.U.H)

Islamic Law is a highly balanced and moderate system. it prescribes a high standard of morality by accommodating the natural weaknesses of man. It observes the social values on the one hand, and also protects the private rights of individuals on the other. Islamic Law encompasses all the essential features which provides the theoretical and practical foundations for a high quality legislation. As a result, this system manifests a high standard of justice. For example, in the case of divorce, it compels the husband to pay the complete dower to her wife. Talaq is also prescribed in the extreme situations, otherwise it is directed the spouses to make compromise with each other. After a woman is given divorce, she can marry another on the expiry of her waiting period. On the contrary, it is a strange rule of western law that if a woman left the house of her husband due to his cruel behavior with her it compels him to pay her maintenance but not allows him to cohabit with her. To prove the allegation of adultery upon each other is a precondition of divorce in the western law. This

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made the men beghairat, as it allowed for a husband to take compensation from the paramour of his wife which is, in fact, a price of her wife's chastity. This opened a way for the false allegations of adultery and make the court as laundry for cleaning these allegations.

On the contrary, islam prescribes waiting period for a woman in the case of talaq to assure that she is not pregnant. If she is pregnant, it is till the delivery, otherwise she can marry on the expiry of three periods. There is nologic to wait for ten months or three hundred days on the contrary. This law is followed in the whole Islamic world. In different European countries, different laws regulate the cases of talaq but all these are imperfect.

In Belgium, Australia, Switzerland and Norway spouses can get a decree of divorce from a court of law by mutual understanding. This law is similar to the khula as in Islamic law.

In Germany if spouses do not cohabit for a period of less than one year it does not amount to divorce this has some resemblance with the *Ila* in Islamic Law. This period is five years in Holland and in Switzerland it is of three years.⁴¹ Rest of the European countries have no law at all in this respect.

There are two prevailing opinions in Islamic law regarding the case of missing husband. one is that the wife should wait for her missing husband for four years. According to second she has to wait him till his return or death. This is the position of Islamic law but in Sweden this duration is 9 years. No law in Europe, else France and Belgium, prescribes a waiting period for a divorced woman i.e. 10 years (in Belgium).⁴²

Comments

This is the position of legal system of the nations which are considered most civilized amongst the world. But a investigation that none of these nations can give a comprehensive and balanced legal system to the world.

Who will analyze this paper impartially will recognize the fact that Islamic law dominates all the laws due to its salient features of justice, balance, protection of social norms, repulsion of harm, morality, and comprehensiveness in all the fields of life. not a single point of such comprehensiveness is found in the other legal systems of world although these laws have been promulgated by the collective wisdom of jurists, philosophers and thinkers of the 19th century after the struggles of one hundred years. these laws cannot compete the that is given by a non-literate person, fourteen centuries ago, without the help of any parliament or legislative body. If still, someone denies the fact that the Islamic law is the product of man's intellect then he must accept for him the divine powers. A man who gave such a wonderful Law to the man kind did not claim to be its originator, but clearly attributed it to the God. A man who denies the need of divine guidance.

Conclusion

1. Islamic law is the only choice for the women who are suppressed and it can play a very important role. In Pakistan, the women are exploited in every walk of life due to the lack of knowledge & awareness of their rights. The rights of woman given to her by Islam can not be exercised in its letter and spirit without recognizing her equal to the men in society. This needs to be a part of social life besides the textbooks.

2. In western civilization the gender equality is limited to slogans and women are not given rights as equal to the men. For instance, there is a big difference between the wages of

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men and women who are working in same scale. The women are paid less as compared to the men. According to surveys, women and children are 77% of the poor population of America. This due to the difference of wages of men and women. An actual equality can not be brought by chanting the slogans only but by working hard for this cause.

3. In Shariah, equal Social, cultural, political and economical for women are recognized as to the men. All the Rights those are available to men are equally granted to women by constitution of Pakistan. These rights include: right of retaliation, right of education, right of speech, right of entrepreneurship, right of organization, right of marriage, right to run a business, protection from defamation & imprisonment etc. but she can not fully enjoy these rights, due to social constraints and superfluous customs. For example, Islam recognizes the right of ownership for a woman but the social norms and poor family values do not allow her to exercise her right of ownership. Similarly, the right of khula is available to woman as to the right of divorce of a man but this right too is not often exercised.

4. All these rights are available to women in Western Society. But it is not a solution of her problems. Her actual problem is described by a French woman as: the women have special moral value. Her view point regarding the humanity is different from that of men but it does not necessarily mean that her theory is the best. Her actual success is to be a woman and not to pose like men unnaturally. Major function of a woman is to take care of children and home management. It is obvious from the studies that the western woman has also wants to be limited to these function.

5. Islam granted the right of ownership, khula, maintenance, custody of children, and dower to the woman but she can not enjoy these rights, due to ignorance. She must be educated in this regard.

6. In west, the woman was denied many of her rights like maintenance, dissolution of marriage etc. one hundred years ago. Although the western civilization granted her these rights quiet a sometime ago, but it also put over her extra burden of financing herself and her children. This resulted in destruction of family system and causes trouble. To reform the family system, it should be incumbent upon man to finance home as well as children. Islam allows a man to marry with four women but with the consent of first wife and must do justice between all of them. Bu the actual position is not so, and most men do not do justice between their wives. In western society, to have the boy friends and girl friends is a common practice due to gender equality. The marriage is a waste of time to them rather it is a burden that should be avoided. It is merely a tool to satisfy sexual desire that can also be fulfilled without marriage. After a comprehensive analysis of both the western and Islamic cultures, we came to the conclusion that only Islam gives a woman to the position she deserves.

7. The woman deserves a respectable position, whether she lives in western society or Islamic society. The study of western culture reveals that the most important factor behind the conversion of young ladies into Islam is its just system that specify different functions for both men and women. These functions are compatible with biological and physical abilities. It has become clear now that the feminism is a misbehavior to the women. This reality is accepted by women and drive them to embrace true faith of islam. islam is a complete code of life and a sole system that protects the right of women. It is the only religion that gave a set of rules for the comfort of woman and guard her from destruction. It gave her that position that was beyond her thought in the environment of evilness and obscenity.

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